

Towards a Dynamic View of UK Deprivation: Harmonising the IMD Using Claimant Count Data

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Summary

Under the United Kingdom's devolution framework, key population datasets have been produced separately by each nation's statistical authority. The incompatibility of national Indices of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) presents challenges for researchers and policymakers seeking to address inequalities across and between UK nations. This paper proposes a method of harmonising the IMD across the UK by combining national IMD indices with a measure of average monthly claimant counts – a statistic underlying the Employment domain score across national IMD indices in the UK. The paper provides perspective on where national IMD indexes may be obscuring patterns of deprivation in the UK in 2025 at a small-area level.

KEYWORDS: Composite Indices, Deprivation Indices, Harmonisation, GIS

1. Introduction

Patterns of deprivation have historically been studied using rather static indices, often derived solely from census data (Norman et al., 2024). The Carstairs and Morris index for Scotland and the Townsend index for England, for example, were constructed using 1981 Census data including information on (male) unemployment, overcrowding, car access, and social class (or house renting in the case of the Townsend Index) (Carstairs & Morris, 1989, 1991; Townsend et al., 1988). Today, the Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) is the UK's official statistic of deprivation, with indices updated approximately every 3 to 5 years since its launch in England in 2000 (Deas et al., 2003; Kiely, 2023). This paper argues that the availability of up-to-date open-access administrative data in recent years has created opportunities to build more timely and dynamic pictures of deprivation in and across UK nations.

Currently, there is no single Index of Multiple Deprivation for Britain or the United Kingdom. Yet, policy interventions developed to tackle deprivation are frequently constructed at the level of the state, which raises important questions about potential biases in resource distribution between nations. Under the UK's devolution framework, each nation's statistical authority currently constructs their own national IMD measure, namely: the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD), the Northern Irish Multiple Deprivation Measure (NIMDM), the English Index of Multiple Deprivation (EIMD in this paper but commonly abbreviated to IMD), and the Welsh Index of Multiple Deprivation (WIMD). While the latest iteration of EIMD and WIMD was published at the end of 2025 (Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government, 2025; Welsh Government, 2025), the most recent SIMD was published in 2020, and the last iteration of NIMDM was published in 2017. There are some differences in the construction of these measures, including in the indicators and domains used to construct them, the geographies they map onto, and the frequency with which they are published, which complicate the extent to which deprivation can currently be studied across the UK.

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1.1. Limitations of Current Approaches

Over the past decade, researchers have developed a growing number of (experimental) methodologies to construct more dynamic and comparable deprivation statistics in the UK. However, these studies have generally focused either on cross-national comparison or on national comparisons over time. Kikuchi et al. (2023) have, for example, used the claimant counts statistic, alongside NHS and policing data, to construct an annual deprivation Index for England. Meanwhile, Lloyd et al. (2022) constructed the UK Deprivation Index (UKDI), which relies on census-derived data on employment, health, and education. Most of these approaches do not directly use the IMD. Indeed, Abel et al. (2016) were the first to argue that income and employment domains are broadly comparable across nations, and it is possible to model national IMD scores as a function of income and employment domain scores, with residuals representing all other domains. In recent years, this methodology has been adapted by Parsons at MySociety to create the ‘Composite 2020 UK Index of Multiple Deprivation’ (2021). Given that Northern Ireland moved away from exclusively using benefit counts to build their income domain score in NIMDM 2017, they only use employment domain scores. However, even within Employment domain scores, there are some differences in domain construction.

2. Methodology

Building on the work of Abel (2016) and Parsons (2021), this paper uses the Claimant Count to harmonise national IMD scores. The Claimant Count (CC) statistic is a measure underlying the employment domain scores of each national IMD and counts working-age people who receive either Jobseekers Allowance or ‘out of work’ Universal Credit. It is published monthly by UK Office for National Statistics (for Great Britain) and the Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency (NISRA). While IMD publications only list Employment domain scores and ranks, underlying indicators like the claimant count can be reconstructed using the same data sources, time periods and population denominators applied in the national IMD.

To create harmonised UK IMD statistics, IMD scores were first modelled as a function of average monthly claimant counts, with the residual variation capturing all other deprivation. National IMD scores were then standardised relative to a target nation (England in this paper) by applying the target nation’s regression coefficients to employment components and scaling the residuals from other nations to match the residual distribution of the target. This approach assumes that standardised residuals are comparable across nations (Abel et al., 2016). While this assumption is not perfectly accurate—given differences in the construction of IMD domains and indicators between nations—it was considered reasonable for producing broadly comparable deprivation scores at a UK-wide scale. Harmonised IMD scores were then reranked and allocated to deciles adjusting for differences in population size between areas. For England and Wales, claimant counts are rebased from 2011 Lower-Level Super Output Areas (LSOA) boundaries to 2021 LSOA boundaries using population-weighted areal interpolation, as NOMIS currently does not provide 2021 LSOA-based data. Additionally, updates to statistical geographies in Northern Ireland and Scotland were made after the publication of their latest IMD therefore 2025 population estimates were rebased to match the geographies used in NIMDM and SIMD.

The paper proceeds in two stages:

- **Comparing UK Models:** The correlation between claimant counts and Employment domain scores is examined for each nation. The model fit and rank displacement of a composite IMD constructed using Employment domain and claimant counts is compared and mapped.
- **Mapping 2025 IMD Displacement:** Mapping out where deciles are significantly displaced when national vs. harmonised scores (claimant count model) and index year vs. 2025 claimant count data are compared.

3. Comparing UK Models: Claimant Count vs. Deprivation Domain

As shown in Table 1., claimant count rates are strongly correlated with the employment deprivation domain across Scotland, England, Northern Ireland, and Wales indicating that the claimant count statistic captures a substantial amount of the variation in IMD employment deprivation scores.

Table 1 Claimant Count and Domain Score Correlation

	NIMDM 2017	SIMD 2020	WIMD 2025	EIMD 2025
IMD Time Period	April 2015 - March 2016	Feb, May, Aug, Nov 2017	April 2022 - March 2023	April 2022 - March 2023
IMD Population Denominator	2016 mid-year working-age population	2017 mid-year working-age population	2022 mid-year working-age population	2022 mid-year working-age population
Claimant Count Correlation	0.89*	0.90	0.85	0.80

* Claimant Count data aggregated across 9 months not 12 as data was not available.

The claimant count statistic explains a substantial portion of the variation in overall IMD scores across the UK nations. However, compared to the employment domain model, the claimant count model captures the official IMD less precisely.

As seen in table 2., while overall displacement patterns are largely similar and (unsurprisingly) almost all areas experienced some rank displacement, the Claimant Count model is better at preserving rank integrity. Particularly in Scotland, rank displacement is notably higher in the claimant count model.

Table 2. Rank Displacement by Model

Statistic	Claimant Count Model			Employment Domain Model		
	Northern Ireland	Scotland	Wales	Northern Ireland	Scotland	Wales
Total %	97.0	93.8	98.0	97.5	99.7	98.9
25%	7.0	3.0	5.5	7.0	54.0	9.0
50%	16.0	6.0	12.5	17.0	137.0	26.5
75%	30.0	10.0	23.0	32.0	274.0	53.5
Small area count	863	6541	1879	868	6958	1896
max	105.0	60.0	331.5	163.0	1376.0	277.5
mean	20.31	7.13	17.34	22.26	188.76	37.31
min	1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	0.5
std	17.34	5.88	18.19	20.19	178.66	37.37

3.1 Deprivation Distributions

Figures 1. and 2. show Wales and Northern Ireland’s population skewed towards lower - more deprived - deciles across both harmonisation models while Scotland’s population is notably skewed towards higher – less deprived – deciles in the Employment Domain Model.

Figure 2. Distribution of Deprivation across UK Nations within each Harmonised IMD Decile
- Claimant Count Model

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4. Mapping Decile Displacement

The map in Figure 3. reveals significant differences between how deciles and claimant count statistics in national IMD indexes compare to harmonised IMD deciles (CC model) and 2025 claimant count statistics.

Figure 3. Bivariate Map of Decile Displacement and Claimant Count Change

5. Conclusion

Both the claimant count and deprivation-domain-based harmonisation models reveal spatial inequalities across UK nations. Furthermore, notable differences were identified between harmonised and national IMD rankings, as well as between 2025 claimant counts and those used in national IMD measures. The findings underscore the need for more dynamic measures of deprivation.

The paper is likely to be of interest to academics and policymakers interested in how the IMD is used to allocate resources across nations and provides a useful reference point for those seeking to understand where IMD metrics may be more or less successful in capturing contemporary patterns of deprivation. As monthly claimant count data are available for all nations, the statistic may also be useful for research on deprivation trajectories and for evaluating IMD-based policy interventions.

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Biography

Johara Meyer is a first-year PhD student at University College of London supervised by James Cheshire and Paul Longley. Her main research interests include the development of spatial statistics and visualisation methodologies for communicating issues of uncertainty and representation in social geographical data science.